

LINGUISTIC ELEMENTS OF SEMANTIC IN ENGLISH

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Annotation

The meaning of the word is not homogenous and can be considered as a structure. One and the same word may have several meanings. Traditionally a word that has more than one meaning is called polysemantic, and the phenomenon polysemy can be defined as plurality of meaning. Polysemy is connected with the phenomenon of the semantic structure of the word and those of the lexico-semantic variant and the seme.

Key words: Semantic, companion, elements, characterized, peripheric, polysemantic, correlates, monotounous, Lingustic, person.

Introduction

There are 2 main approaches to the problem of the semantic structure. The 1st (among the scholars are A.I. Smirnitsky and V.V.Vinogradov) deals with LSVs, which are defined as minimal doublefacet lexical units, the outer facet(formal) of which is the sound form and the inner side (facet) is one of the meanings of a concrete word. The semantic structure then is defined as a structured set of lexico-semantic variants. E.g. companion n.1) a person, who goes somewhere or spends time with somebody – John is my close companion 2) a person, usually a womn, paid to live with an elderly or sick person- The old lady`s companion always drives the car 3) a pair or set of things – I had a companion to that vase, but I broke it.4) a book that explains how to do smth(handbook) – the Motorist`s companion

The LSVs within the semantic structure of one word consist in various relations. Thus there are those which appeared first (if we study them diachronically), those which are used more often than others etc. As in any system

there is the center and periphery. The meaning can be direct or nominative, when it just nominates the object without the help of context, e.g. in titles. figurative when the object is named and characterized through its similarity with another object., e.g. a hand –рука: стрелка часов. Other oppositions are main or primary :: secondary, central :: peripheric, The main meaning is that which possesses the highest frequency at the present stage of development.

There are 2 types of development of meanings or relations between LSVs- 1) irradiation (radial)- 2)chain. E.g. the word portion has 8 meanings 1) a part of anything, a share 2) a quantity of food for one person 3) a quantity of any kind of food served in a restaurant 4) the share of an estate given to an heir 5) marriage portion – dowry 6) a person`s fate 7) a part of any whole 8) a part of the whole stock, a limited quantity – a portion of water : 1,7,5,6,2,4 – radial; 1-2-3 –chain, 1-7-8 chain.

According to I.V. Arnold, polysemy is inherent in the very nature of words, as they always contain a generalization of several traits of the object. Polysemy is characteristic of most words in many languages. It is one of the characteristics of the English vocabulary as compared with Russian, due to the monosyllabic character of English and the predominance of root words. The greater the relative frequency of the word, the greater the number of elements that constitute its semantic structure, i.e. the more polysemantic it is.

Polysemy and semantic structure exist only in language, not in speech.

The meaning in speech is contextual. If we examine one word in two different contexts we can see that a definite context particularizes it and makes possible only one meaning. Usage correlates each time only with one meaning of the word. E.g. 1) Most birds and some insects fly 2) A bee flew through the open window 3) I prefer flying to going by train 4) Time flies. Speaking about contextual variants scholars speak about usual (узуальный) and occasional (оказиональный)

meaning e.g. to drone v. has 2 usual meanings 1) to make a low humming sound as made by bees 2) to talk or sing in a low monotonous voice. – An occasional meaning – to move producing a droning sound – A car droned along the street.

Polysemy does not interfere with the communicative function of the language because in every particular case the situation and context, cancel all the unnecessary meanings.

The 2nd approach deals with semes and defines them as the minimal unit of meaning. Here special procedures of componential analysis were developed to determine the components of each meaning and represent this as a combination of elementary senses. The meaning of the word son may be described as belonging to the terms of kinship and denoting a direct male offspring of the first generation, while grandson is a direct male offspring of the second generation. If compared with such words as artist, coward, friend, lass or visitor these words will reveal a common denominator in the very general meaning ‘person’ that constitutes the lexico-grammatical meaning of personal nouns.

Conclusion

The language is the discipline where originally the semantics concept was introduced. Linguistic semantics is the study of the meaning of language words . Linguistic semantics contrasts with three other aspects that intervene in an expression with meaning: syntax and pragmatics . Semantics is the study of the meaning attributable to syntactically well-formed expressions. The syntax studies only the rules and principles on how to construct semantically interpretable expressions from simpler expressions, but in itself it does not allow to attribute meanings. Semantics examines the way in which meanings were attributed to words, their modifications throughtime and even its changes for new meanings. The lexicography is another part of the semantics that tries to describe the meaning of the words of a language at a given moment and often display their results in the preparation of dictionaries.

On the other hand, pragmatics refers to how circumstances and context help to decide between alternatives of use or interpretation; Thanks to pragmatics, language can be used for humorous or ironic purposes. In addition, pragmatics reduces the ambiguity of expressions, selecting only an appropriate set of interpretations in a given context.

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